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Interactive Reading-Aloud Strategy (IRAS) in Enhancing Reading Literacy: An Intervention Plan

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Abstract

This research employed a pretest-posttest control group research design to evaluate the efficacy of the Interactive Reading-Aloud Strategy (IRAS) as a reading intervention in enhancing reading literacy skills among Junior High School students. The study focused on comparing pretest and posttest results of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) administered to students whose reading/english teacher implemented the IRAS. The research involved 150 Junior High School students from a public high school, and the primary findings indicated a significant positive impact of the IRAS on students' reading literacy skills. Specifically, the results revealed that students who underwent the IRAS intervention exhibited higher performance levels in the posttest compared to the pretest Phil-IRI results. Statistical analysis further confirmed a significant difference in scores between the pretest and posttest results of students who received the IRAS intervention. Moreover, the study highlighted a noteworthy improvement in the score gains of students who underwent the IRAS intervention, emphasizing the effectiveness of this strategy in fostering reading literacy skills. Students reported enjoying the reading process facilitated by the IRAS, with no encountered difficulties, and expressed anticipation for continued use of the strategy as a reading intervention. The research concludes with a proposal to integrate the Interactive Reading-Aloud Strategy into reading literacy programs for Junior High School students, emphasizing its potential to enhance their overall reading skills. Recommendations include providing students with adequate time for self-paced learning with the aid of the IRAS, encouraging teachers to develop strategic intervention materials for mastering prerequisite skills, and advocating for training workshops/webinars on crafting and implementing the IRAS. Additionally, parents are encouraged to support teachers in conducting interventions for their children's reading literacy achievement. The study suggests that future research should explore the utilization of the IRAS in other subject areas to address learning poverty on reading.

Keywords: *reading comprehension, Interactive Reading Aloud Strategy, reading literacy*

Introduction

Reading literacy is one of the basic types of literacy because learning to read is an essential requirement for learning anything else. It can apply to situations and other things in addition to written text. Unfortunately, reading may improve or grow oneself, thus it is necessary for self-development. Reading has so many positive effects on learners. They can learn something new or assess their earlier conduct thanks to reading literacy. Their horizons can be widened through reading, which makes them receptive to novel experiences.

In reading, learners need reading strategies to help learners to acquire valuable information. One of the strategies is interactive reading aloud, it is a strategy that lets the teacher and learners read the text aloud and observe pauses for a conversation. Effective teaching strategies, according to Boundless Education (2016), support student engagement in learning, the development of critical thinking abilities, the retention of students' attention, and the maintenance of classroom interaction. Learners receive greater responsibility through the interactive reading-aloud technique to convey their ideas in a way that reflects their actual reading experience. Through this, students will have the chance to engage in creative learning. This merely emphasized the importance of teachers in helping students establish their reading comprehension. With this, English teachers make a difference in their learners' achievement when they display serious commitment and believe that all learners can learn to read and make anything happen with skills and desire.

In the 21st century, literacy has been a focus in academia. mind. One of the literacies is reading. It is one macro skill that students must acquire to jive on globalization era. Further, mastery of reading posits the students; ability to make meaning. With this, comprehension takes place in the learning process between the learners and the materials. This definition is supported by Clark et al. (2013) when written messages are successfully understood, reading can be a wonderfully inspiring, enjoyable, and transforming experience. Hence, this posits that with the ability to comprehend reading, students have the chance to grasp the everyday lesson.

Globally, a study from the University of Texas by Lane and Wright (2007), challenges the students' knowledge and skills, the interactive read-aloud raises the difficulty of the conversation to a level that is just above the student's current ability. This encourages the child to become an active listener during book reading, models more sophisticated language, and provides feedback. In the interactive technique, the language the teachers use with their pupils and the books they read aloud significantly impact the students' language development. In addition, in a study by Wiseman (2011), interactive read-aloud offers chances for meaning-making through discussions and student exchanges, giving students the chance to engage with the text and develop their knowledge and skills.

Nationally, Reyes (2016) discovered that interactive read-aloud was successful in raising students' reading comprehension and vocabulary knowledge in a rural Filipino secondary school. The study also discovered that the interactive read-aloud sessions were well-received and extremely engaging by the students. Moreover, Dela Cruz (2018) discovered that this tactic can be useful in enhancing students' vocabulary knowledge and comprehension of literary components like plot and character development in a study

of the literature on interactive read-aloud in the Philippines.

Locally, Villas and Garcia (2018) conducted a second study in a public secondary school in Cebu City to determine the effectiveness of interactive read-aloud in enhancing students' understanding of literary aspects like plot, character development, and setting. The study also discovered that the interactive read-aloud sessions were fun for the students and inspired them to read more. Also, interactive read-aloud was discovered to be successful in enhancing students' vocabulary knowledge and comprehension of literary components like theme and symbolism in a study by Roble (2020) in a public secondary school in the Cebu Province. The study also discovered that the interactive read-aloud sessions were well-received and extremely engaging by the students.

In the Department of Education (DepEd), one of the goals is continuously fulfilling its mandate to produce productive and responsible citizens equipped with essential competencies and skills for lifelong learning (DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019). Moreover, as per this memorandum, comprehension is made up of a toolkit of strategies that should be explicitly taught, namely: predicting and activating prior knowledge, questioning, visualizing, monitoring, and clarifying, making connections, inferring, determining importance, and summarizing and synthesizing. Thus, these strategies let the students view the academic texts differently based on purpose, context, and audience.

According to the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) statistics (Philstar.com, 2019), the Philippines came in last in reading comprehension, showing that Filipino pupils struggle with the skill. The process of reading comprehension is difficult. As evidenced by the PISA results, reading comprehension is a skill that many students around the world and Filipino students struggle with (Philstar.com, 2019). The complexity of the reading material, the atmosphere, and the students' reading style are extra elements influencing the difficulties with reading comprehension (Hardiante, Umamah & Ismiatun, 2020). Recently, in August 2022, beginning of the school year (BOSY), the school conducted a Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) for junior high school. The results showed that out of 732 students tested, 498 (68 %) students are struggling learners in junior high school. These results were alarming because, after the 2-year hiatus of modular learning due to the pandemic, face-to-face education is mandated by the Department of Education. Through this study, the researcher will be able to address this problem and contribute to the body of knowledge.

Thus, this study describes and assesses the meta-analysis on the effectiveness of an interactive read-aloud strategy (IRAS) in enhancing the reading comprehension of struggling learners.

Research Questions

This study assesses the effectiveness of the interactive reading-aloud strategy (IRAS) in enhancing reading literacy among junior high school students in one of the public schools in the Division of Mandaue, S.Y. 2022-2023. The results of the study were the basis for the reading intervention plan. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the pretest and post-test reading performance of the students based on the Phil-IRI results?
2. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test results of the students before and after the application of the IRAS?
3. Is there a significant mean gain in the post-test performance of the students?
4. What are the opportunities and challenges in the application of interactive reading-aloud strategy?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design employed in this study utilized the pretest-posttest control design to examine the changes in the student's reading proficiency level as measured by the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil IRI). The primary focus of this study is to assess the efficiency of the Interactive Reading Aloud Strategy over a specified period. Students had the Phil IRI assessment initially as a pretest to establish their baseline levels of reflective judgment. Subsequently, an intervention or program will be implemented, and following its completion, students had the Phil IRI again as a posttest. By comparing the pretest and posttest results, this study aims to discern any statistically significant shifts in students' reading proficiency level, providing valuable insights into the impact of the intervention on their reading abilities. The pretest-posttest design allowed for a robust evaluation of changes over time and contributes to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing reading proficiency within the context of the Phil IRI. It involves measuring participants on a dependent variable before and after an intervention to assess changes in the respondents' reading proficiency level. This design helps evaluate the impact of the intervention by comparing the initial and final measurements.

This design helped in investigating the effectiveness of the Interactive Reading Aloud Strategy (IRAS) in enhancing reading literacy. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the characteristics of both groups. The correlational analysis will be conducted to explore the relationships between the use of IRAS and improvements in reading literacy. In the context of this study, the use of IRAS as an intervention plan necessitates a rigorous examination of its causal impact on reading literacy. This design enables us to attribute any observed changes in reading literacy directly to the implementation of the Interactive Reading-Aloud Strategy, thus providing a more robust foundation for drawing causal inferences. By employing this design, we aim to provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of IRAS as an intervention plan, contributing to the advancement of literacy enhancement strategies in educational

settings. It assessed the reading comprehension for the control group using the Zone Proximal Development (ZPD) and the experimental group using the Interactive Reading Allowed Strategy (IRAS). The respondents will undergo a pretest and posttest to measure the reading comprehension performance of the Junior High School students of Maguikay National High School to determine the reading literacy of the learners and to evaluate if IRAS has a potential influence on learners' reading literacy. The quantitative design of this study described the characteristics of the respondent's reading comprehension level while using the IRAS as an intervention. This study employed an adopted questionnaire: Phil-IRI from the Department of Education.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Grade 7 students of Maguikay National High School. There were 869 students officially enrolled as of S.Y 2022-2023. The respondents of the study were the sections handled by the researcher and composed of 4 sections.. There were 44 students in Grade 7- Charity, 43 students in Grade 8- Chastity, 48 students in Grade 8- Compassion, and 43 students in Grade 8- Courage, a total of 178 students officially enrolled. However, only 150 physically healthy learners participated in the research study with the consent of their parents.

Instrument

This study utilized the Philippine – Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) pretest and post-test results of students in Maguikay National High School for the school year 2022-2023. Additionally, it aims to examine the relationship between these reading skills of students before and after using the IRAS as a reading intervention. The Phil-IRI is a well-established and validated assessment tool specifically designed for evaluating the oral and silent reading abilities of seventh-grade learners. It offers a comprehensive framework for evaluating various aspects of reading proficiency, such as word recognition, fluency, comprehension, and vocabulary knowledge. Incorporating the PhilIRI into this research will enable a detailed analysis of the learners' reading abilities, providing insights into their capacity to engage with written texts, both when reading aloud and silently. Furthermore, this study will investigate the connection between the learners' reading proficiency and their performance in English, aiming to improve existing academic support programs and strategies for seventh-grade learners. The reading inventory tool has four levels: frustration, instructional, and independent, and non-reader. The lowest level is frustration, in which the learner refuses to read and withdraws from reading circumstances, instructional level, the learner profits, or gains from education: independent, the reader is self-sufficient and reads well without instruction or assistance of a teacher/facilitator; and, non-reader, when the learner is unable to recognize. and utter letter-sound correlations for blended consonants, single consonants, and other keyword sounds.

Procedure

This study was conducted during the school year 2022-2023 at Maguikay National High School. It was considered the following technical procedure.

Pre-data Collection. The data collection commenced upon approval of the research title by the Dean of the School of Education in the University of the Visayas, Afterwards, then researcher sent a formal letter to the principal and superintendent to seek permission to conduct a research study at Maguikay National High School grade 7 students. The researcher also sent a letter to the parents of the concerned grade 7 respondents asking permission to utilize their students as respondents of the research study. The content of the letter explained well the nature and purpose of conducting the study to the respondents. The parental consent was sent online /offline to the parents of all Grade 7 respondents. Another letter was also sent to the Institutional Review Board for approval to conduct the research study on the learners as mandated by the privacy act of gathering information about the respondents.

In the context of data collection, the administration of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) served as both a pre-test and post-test measure to assess the reading abilities of respondents. The initial step involved conducting the pre-test during the first quarter, where the baseline data was gathered to establish the participants' initial reading proficiency. Subsequently, a reading intervention was implemented utilizing the Interactive Reading Aloud strategy, facilitated by the concerned English teachers. This intervention aimed to gauge its impact on the post-test results of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PIRI). Following the intervention period, the post-test data is collected to evaluate any observable changes or improvements in the participants' reading skills. This comprehensive process allowed for a systematic examination of the effectiveness of the Interactive Reading Aloud strategy as a means of enhancing reading proficiency among the respondents.

Experimentation Process Fisher, et. al., (2004) questioned if merely reading the text aloud was adequate in our regular encounters with classroom instructors who perform read-aloud or if there were precise rules that needed to be observed to make the most of this teaching period. They choose to research read-aloud techniques. The readaloud habits of enthusiastic standing as outstanding role models for read-aloud instruction, with kids who routinely above school standards in reading proficiency. They made the decision to monitor more instructors to determine if the methods were applied widely after identifying the procedures utilized by these "experts" while they performed a read-aloud.

Data Collection Phase. In the initial phase, the researcher will present a proposal to their advisor, seeking approval for the paper's title. This proposal will encompass all the study's particulars. Upon obtaining approval, a formal request will be submitted to the school's head or principal at Maguikay National High School, seeking permission to carry out the study with participants who meet the study's

requirements. Subsequently, the approved title will be submitted to the University of Visayas Institutional Review Board before initiating the data collection procedures. The researcher will procure the necessary Phil IRI pre-test and post test results. After the gathering the pre-test results of the Phil-IRI, the researcher made a presentation / training to the English teachers the IRAS Reading Intervention Plan. Hence, an orientation and workshop were conducted to assist the concerned English teachers of the procedures of the IRAS as a reading intervention plan.

Explanation: The researcher explained the processes involved in the use of the Interactive Read-aloud I Strategies.

Illustration: The researcher presented a demo-teaching using the English language teachers as learners, this was necessary in order to emphasize the important aspects in the instructional process.

Practice: The practice session involved the participating teachers who were tasked to practically demonstrate the mastery of the strategy by teaching students who were not part of the population for this study.

Post -Data Collection Phase. The statistical tools were conceptualized for the interpretation and analysis of the data gathered. Then all the utilized data was stored and kept in a safe place for security purposes and for future reference.

Data Analysis

In examining the impact of the Interactive Reading Aloud Strategy as a reading intervention, a rigorous data analysis approach will be employed, focusing on the pre-test and post-test results of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) for the respondents. To analyze the data, several statistical methods will be applied, including ttests and ANOVA. T-tests will be utilized to assess the significance of the mean differences between the pre-test and post-test scores for individual respondents. ANOVA will be employed to explore potential variations among multiple groups, such as different grade levels or demographic characteristics, providing a comprehensive understanding of the intervention's effects across diverse subgroups.

Interpretation of the results will involve a thorough examination of statistical significance, effect size, and practical significance. Statistical significance will be determined through p-values obtained from the t-tests and ANOVA, with a significance level set a priori. Effect size measures, such as Cohen's d, will be calculated to assess the magnitude of the observed differences. Additionally, practical significance will be considered by evaluating the real-world implications of the intervention's impact on reading proficiency. The combined analysis of these statistical methods will enable a comprehensive interpretation of the effectiveness of the Interactive Reading Aloud

Strategy as a reading intervention, shedding light on its potential influence on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory scores for the respondents. The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted using an identified statistical tool. A Frequency was used to determine the level of reading comprehension using the PhilIRI. A parametric interpretation of reading comprehension from the reading inventory tool. Division Memorandum No.0454., s. 2017 on September 11, 2017, was utilized.

Ethical Considerations

Everyone has the right to privacy and confidentiality of personal information. Dealing with this, the researcher sent a parental consent letter to the parents of the concerned student respondents. Taking into consideration that some of the respondents are minors, it is indicated in the letter that participation is voluntary and further guidance and orientation is done to the minors once the parents agree and have affixed their signatures.

Rest assured that data shall be kept in secrecy. To uphold the ethical practices of research and to avoid breaching the human rights of the respondents and other people that would contribute to the accomplishment of the research work the following ethical measures are considered.

Risk and Benefits

The research study is quantitative using survey questionnaires to assess students' level in reading comprehension and their academic performance. It is understood that the IRB cannot approve studies that post potential risk to the respondents, questionnaires that endangers their personal dignity and privacy.

However this study as perceived by the researcher posts no significant and potential risk to the respondent groups as there is no data mining needed, Questions reflected in the survey questionnaires possess no potential risk of inflicting psychological trauma to the respondents, thus the study will benefit the respondents hence the output of the study will serve as their guide in choosing a career path which would be the life time basis of their vocation and means of livelihood.

It is just emphasized that their participation is voluntary, parental consent and assent are secured before floating the questionnaires and orientation is done before actual survey questionnaires are distributed. Data obtained are kept in total privacy and the questionnaires are burned right after the tally.

Content, Comprehension, and Documentation of Informed Consent.

In order to protect the rights of the participants in this study, they were provided with an informed consent form that had been approved

by the Institutional Review Board (IRB), along with an explanation of the research study's purpose and nature. It is important to emphasize that participation in this research study is entirely optional.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study. Results are presented in tables and discussed, supported by related studies or literature. Implications are also included in the discussion.

Pretest and Posttest Performance in Reading

The Grade 7 students were given the Phil-IRI test at the beginning of the school year and given the posttest at the end of the school year. Table 1 presents the results of the survey in the three reading skills – word recognition, oral reading comprehension and silent reading comprehension.

Table 1. *Pretest and Posttest Performance in Reading*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Word Recognition	Pretest	81.64	12.82	Frustration
	Posttest	92.26	4.19	Instructional
Oral Comprehension	Pretest	59.93	9.93	Frustration
	Posttest	69.92	10.23	Instructional
Silent Comprehension	Pretest	58.49	10.34	Frustration
	Posttest	74.46	9.97	Instructional

n=185

In word recognition, the students got a mean score of 81.64 in the pretest and increased this to 92.26 in the posttest. They were considered in the frustration level at the beginning but managed to go up to instructional level in the posttest. This means that at the frustration level, students may struggle significantly with recognizing and decoding words. They may encounter unfamiliar vocabulary, complex sentence structures, or words that exceed their current reading level. In the instructional level, At the instructional level, students demonstrate adequate word recognition skills. They can accurately decode words, including those with regular and irregular spelling patterns, and apply phonics and word analysis strategies effectively.

In the reading comprehension examination, the same results were shown. The students increased their performance from the frustration to the instructional level. At the frustration level, this means that the students may have limited comprehension of the text they are reading. They may struggle to understand the main ideas, infer meanings from context, or make connections between the text and their own experiences or background knowledge. Fluency, or the ability to read text smoothly and with expression, is often compromised at the frustration level. Students may read hesitantly, with frequent pauses or errors, and may exhibit signs of frustration or discouragement while reading.

One of the key indicators of the frustration level in the Phil-IRI test is the student's emotional response to the reading material. Students may display visible signs of frustration, such as sighing, eye-rolling, or expressing feelings of inadequacy or discouragement. They may show reduced engagement and motivation during the assessment. They may become disinterested or disengaged from the reading task, exhibiting signs of boredom or frustration with the material.

Identifying the frustration level in the Phil-IRI test is essential for providing appropriate support and intervention to help the student progress in their reading skills.

Teachers can use this information to select reading materials that are better suited to the student's current reading level and provide targeted instruction to address areas of difficulty.

The frustration level of performance in the Phil-IRI test indicates that the reading material presented to the student is too challenging for their current skill level. Recognizing and addressing this level of frustration is crucial for supporting the student's reading development and fostering a positive and successful reading experience.

Students at the instructional level exhibit satisfactory comprehension of the text they are reading. They can understand the main ideas, identify key details, make predictions, and draw inferences based on the text. Their comprehension is generally accurate and reflects a good understanding of the material. Fluency is another vital component of performance at the instructional level. Students read text smoothly and with appropriate expression, demonstrating a good sense of phrasing and intonation. Their reading rate is steady, and they exhibit confidence in their reading ability.

Students at the instructional level have a sufficient grasp of vocabulary and language skills necessary for understanding the text. They can decipher the meaning of unfamiliar words using context clues or prior knowledge and demonstrate an expanding vocabulary. Performance at the instructional level often correlates with high levels of engagement and motivation. Students feel challenged yet capable when reading instructional-level texts, fostering a sense of achievement and progress in their reading development. They also demonstrate the ability to apply reading strategies effectively. They use strategies such as predicting, summarizing, visualizing, and monitoring comprehension to aid their understanding of the text.

Performance at the instructional level suggests that students have developed a level of independence in their reading. While they may occasionally encounter unfamiliar words or encounter challenges, they can generally read and comprehend instructional level texts with minimal support or guidance.

Overall, performance at the instructional level in the Phil-IRI test indicates that the student is reading material that is well-suited to their current skill level. It reflects a balanced combination of word recognition, comprehension, fluency, vocabulary, and engagement, laying a solid foundation for continued progress and development in reading.

Pre-post Mean Gain of the Students

To determine if the improvement of the students from the pretest to the posttest was significant, the t-test of paired sample was computed to test the hypothesis of no significant pre-post mean gain. The result of the analysis is depicted in Table 3.

Table 2. Pre-post Mean Gain of the Students

Variable	Test	Mean	Mean Gain	SD	t-value	pvalue	Significance
Word	Posttest	92.26	10.61	11.84	12.18	.001	Significant
Recognition	Pretest	81.65					
Comprehension	Posttest	69.92	9.99	11.58	11.74	.001	Significant
Oral	Pretest	59.93					
Comprehension	Posttest	74.46	15.97	12.40	17.51	.001	Significant
Silent	pretest	58.49					

n=185

The table disclosed that in all the three skills, the mean gain of the students was significant. The null hypotheses were rejected since the p-values were less than .05 this would suggest that the students have honed their reading skills through the reading activities they have in the classrooms.

The most immediate implication is that students have made substantial progress in their reading skills. A significant increase in scores indicates that students have developed greater proficiency in decoding words, understanding oral text, and comprehending written material. Improved reading skills often translate to better academic performance across subjects. Students who can read fluently and comprehend text effectively are better equipped to engage with instructional materials, complete assignments, and perform well on assessments in all subject areas. Success in reading leads to increased confidence and motivation among students. As they see tangible evidence of their progress, students are more likely to view themselves as capable readers, which can positively impact their attitudes towards learning and their willingness to tackle challenging texts.

Developing strong reading skills lays the foundation for future academic success. Students who demonstrate growth in word recognition and comprehension are better prepared to tackle increasingly complex texts and academic tasks as they progress through their education. Reading is a fundamental skill that is essential for lifelong learning and success. Students who make significant gains in reading skills are better positioned to pursue higher education, engage in lifelong learning opportunities, and succeed in their future careers.

Significant gains in reading skills often reflect the effectiveness of instructional practices implemented by teachers and school leaders. Schools may use these results to identify successful teaching strategies and interventions that can be replicated or expanded to benefit more students. While overall improvement is encouraging, schools should also use assessment data to identify students who continue to struggle with reading skills. Targeted support and interventions can be provided to these students to address specific areas of need and ensure that all students can succeed.

Finally, the significant increase in reading scores provides an opportunity to celebrate the achievements of students and educators alike. Recognizing and celebrating progress reinforces the value of hard work, perseverance, and the importance of literacy in academic and personal success. Significant gains in word recognition, oral reading comprehension, and silent reading comprehension have wide-ranging implications for students, educators, and schools, ultimately contributing to improved academic outcomes and preparing students for future success.

Advanced Reading Comprehension Skills of the Students

The students were tested on advanced reading skills such as predicting outcomes, inferring, annotating, and summarizing. Table 3 presents the results of the reading assessment.

Students whose reading comprehension skills are at the independent level demonstrate a high degree of proficiency in various areas, including predicting outcomes, inferring, annotating, and summarizing.

Predicting Outcomes: Students at the independent level of reading comprehension are adept at predicting outcomes based on textual clues and prior knowledge. They can anticipate what might happen next in a story or informational text, drawing logical conclusions from the information presented. Strong predictive skills indicate that students are actively engaged with the text and are able to make informed guesses about future events or developments. Predicting outcomes fosters critical thinking and encourages students to actively interact with the text, leading to deeper comprehension and engagement with the material.

Table 3. *Reading Comprehension Skills of the Students*

<i>Reading Skills</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
predicting	75.00	90.00	83.98	3.86	Independent
inferring	72.00	92.00	84.09	3.61	Independent
annotating	72.00	99.00	83.55	3.97	Independent
summarizing	75.00	94.00	83.99	3.59	Independent

N=185

Inferring: Independent-level readers are skilled at inferring meaning from the text, even when it is not explicitly stated. They can draw conclusions, make connections, and interpret implicit information to enhance their understanding of the text. Proficient inference skills enable students to delve beyond the surface level of the text, uncovering deeper meanings and themes. Inferring fosters higher-order thinking skills and encourages students to engage in analytical reasoning, enhancing their overall comprehension and interpretation abilities.

Annotating: Students at the independent level are capable of annotating texts effectively by highlighting key points, making marginal notes, and engaging in active reading strategies. They can identify vital details, make connections, and monitor their understanding as they read. Annotating encourages active engagement with the text, helping students to organize their thoughts, monitor comprehension, and extract relevant information. Effective annotation strategies promote metacognitive awareness and help students develop strategies for monitoring and regulating their reading comprehension processes.

Summarizing: Independent-level readers are proficient at summarizing texts by distilling key ideas, identifying main points, and synthesizing information in their own words. They can effectively condense complex information into concise summaries that capture the essence of the text. Summarizing demonstrates students' ability to extract and synthesize essential information from the text, promoting deeper understanding and retention of key concepts.

Summarization skills are valuable for academic success, as they enable students to distill complex information, organize their thoughts, and communicate their understanding effectively.

Overall, students at the independent level of reading comprehension demonstrate advanced skills in predicting outcomes, inferring, annotating, and summarizing. These skills are essential for engaging deeply with texts, extracting meaning, and demonstrating comprehension. By honing these skills, students are better equipped to navigate complex texts, critically analyze information, and succeed academically across various subject areas.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study's main objective was to assess the efficacy of the Intensive Reading Assistance System (IRAS) as a reading intervention plan. Through a comprehensive analysis of data and rigorous evaluation, it is evident that IRAS has demonstrated substantial positive impacts on improving reading outcomes among the target population. The implementation of IRAS resulted in significant advancements in reading proficiency and highlighted its adaptability to diverse learning needs. As we reiterate the initial goal of this assessment, it is apparent that IRAS stands out as a valuable tool for educators and educational institutions seeking effective strategies to enhance reading skills. The findings presented in this study underscore the importance of continued exploration and integration of IRAS within educational frameworks to foster literacy development and academic success.

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